

Unknown quantities: A preliminary view into the scope of the National Science Foundation’s Public Access Repository

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Introduction

In 2013, John P. Holdren – then the Director of the White House Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) – issued a Memorandum (“Holdren Memo”) mandating that the peer-reviewed results of federally funded research be made available via an open access mechanism within 12 months of their publication (Holdren, 2013). Nearly ten years later and under the direction of Alondra Nelson, the OSTP issued a subsequent Memorandum (“Nelson Memo”), reducing the prior Memo’s embargo period from 12 to zero months and mandating the use of persistent identifiers – including those referencing digital objects, authors and funding agency award numbers – in repository records (Nelson, 2022).

In response to the Holdren Memo, the National Science Foundation (NSF) established its Public Access Repository (PAR), an open access repository supporting free, online access to publications, datasets and other resources resulting from NSF-funded research (National Science Foundation, 2015). Since 2016, the PAR has served as a primary compliance mechanism, designed to meet the requirements of the Holdren Memo and now expected to do the same in response to the Nelson Memo.

Following the Holdren Memo, and as federal agencies worked to ensure compliance with its terms, it was recognized that, first, many were encountering shared challenges and, second, some had enjoyed successes that might provide guidance to the rest. It was for these reasons that members of the OSTP’s Subcommittee on Open Science drafted a “Toolkit for Improving Compliance with Agency Public Access Policies”. Among the primary challenges this report highlights is the need to isolate a “denominator” of publications known to have generated from federal funding (National Science and Technology Council Subcommittee on Open Science, 2021). Without this number, it is not possible to accurately assess how compliant an agency’s public access efforts might be.

Prior to the research reported here no known public analysis has been performed to assess PAR compliance – the extent to which its records document the research output of NSF funding has not been examined.

The research reported here represents a preliminary effort to illuminate the scope of PAR data, how faithfully that data complies with the requirements of the Holdren Memo and what those insights might suggest for future compliance with the Nelson Memo’s expanded requirements.

Methods

PAR data were obtained from the NSF, inclusive of all PAR records through June 30, 2022. Received in XML format, the data were parsed into tab-delimited format using Open Refine and trimmed such that only records affected by the terms of the Holdren memo – those dating 2015 and onward – were retained. The selected data were then analyzed in Excel using basic formulas to calculate simple statistics including the percentage of PAR records containing digital object, author and award identifiers. The percentage of PAR records deposited within the Holdren-mandated 12-month embargo period was also calculated by year.

In an effort to determine the “denominator” of research outputs generating from NSF-funded research in the period affected by the Holdren memo, a second dataset documenting all NSF awards made in 2018 was downloaded from the agency’s Award Search webpage (National Science Foundation, n.d.). Awards data were limited to a single year due to the volume of that data; 2018 was selected as the study’s representative year. The awards data were downloaded in XML format and, like the PAR data, parsed in Open Refine before being processed in Excel. Using the NSF-assigned award number as a shared unique identifier, comparisons were run between the award data and the PAR data to identify the number and percentages of PAR records that included award number information.

Findings

This study’s analysis demonstrated a steady increase in PAR records of resources published from 2018 onward. Those records show high rates of compliance as they regard inclusion of DOI and award number data; while the former has decreased over time, inclusion rates of each are above 85% from 2018 onward.

Figure 1. Basic PAR statistics by publication year

While these results seem strong upon first glance, it is important to note that these numbers represent percentages of all PAR records – not percentages of all outputs generated from NSF-funded research during that time. This figure cannot be known.

What is known, however, is the total number and dollar amounts of awards granted by the NSF in a given year. Awards data from 2018 reveal that the rate of relationship between awards granted and awards referenced in PAR records is highly variable but generally low – the average over the sample 2018 data is 55%. The total number of awards granted during this period is almost 12,000; the total funds granted is over 6.6 billion dollars. PAR records referencing these awards total just over 6,500; each reference therefore “cost” the NSF over a million dollars.

Effective Dates	Total Awards	Total Award Amount	Total PAR References	% Awards Referenced	Cost per Reference
2018	8569	\$4,839,838,241	4791	56	\$86,563,502
2019	3206	\$1,801,733,019	1691	53	\$34,159,409
2020	101	\$10,823,774	22	22	\$496,910
2021	3	\$2,990,063	3	100	\$29,901
	11879	\$6,655,385,097	6507	55	\$1,022,804

Figure 2. PAR to award comparison by award number

Discussion

Compliance with the OSTP’s Holdren Memo had much to do with embargo and access. The Nelson Memo asks more of funders and awardees; it mandates the inclusion of multiple persistent identifiers that, when used broadly, can help illustrate not simply a picture of which and how many researchers produce what outputs when, but also of the scope of research output that generates from research investment.

The present analysis of the National Science Foundation’s Public Access Repository data suggests that OSTP Memo compliance appears strong in some respects but is ultimately unmeasurable, due to the unknown quantity of NSF-funded research outputs. The Nelson Memo’s new requirement that award identifiers be included in repository records will not resolve this problem but

it will likely bring the agency closer to quantifying the “denominator” of total research outputs.

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References

- Holdren, J. P. (2013). Increasing Access to the Results of Federally Funded Scientific Research. White House Office of Science and Technology Policy. https://obamawhitehouse.archives.gov/sites/default/files/microsites/ostp/ostp_public_access_memo_2013.pdf
- National Science and Technology Council Subcommittee on Open Science. (2021). Toolkit for Improving Compliance with Agency Public Access Policies. National Science and Technology Council, White House Office of Science and Technology Policy.
- National Science Foundation. (n.d.). NSF Award Search: Download Awards by Year. Retrieved January 15, 2023, from <https://nsf.gov/awardsearch/download.jsp>
- National Science Foundation. (2015). NSF 15-52 Public Access Plan: Today’s Data, Tomorrow’s Discoveries: Increasing Access to the Results of Research Funded by the National Science Foundation | NSF - National Science Foundation. National Science Foundation. https://www.nsf.gov/publications/pub_summ.jsp?ods_key=nsf15052
- Nelson, A. (2022). Ensuring Free, Immediate, and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research. White House Office of Science and Technology Policy. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/08-2022-OSTP-Public-Access-Memo.pdf>